

Zr-Sn-Fe-Cr Alloy Anodized in AA and CA, it's multidisiplinary applications in Industry everyday life science & technology

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Abstract

This research article purpose is for educational purpose including different institutions in science and technology. The advanced zircaloy material i.e. Zircaloy-4 is also known as Zr-Sn-Fe-Cr alloy surface studied in 0.05M ammonium acetate + 0.05M citric acid by using galvanostatic anodic polarization. The purpose of this research study is to identify oxide films based on Zircaloy-4 with electrolytes was determined between the electrolyte composition and the film structures. The enhanced results have been seen as a anodization rate, current efficiency and differential field. It has very importance as a cladding material in nuclear power plants. Under loss of coolant accident, oxidation of Zr-Sn-Fe-Cr alloy compromise the safety of the nuclear power plants by accelerating hydrogen production. Nuclear applications are Fuel cladding, structural components and reactor components. When this alloy is used in nuclear service, it absorbs less hydrogen than zircaloy-2 if exposed to corrosion in water and steam. Due to tremendous resistant to corrosion by many organic acids, inorganic acids and alkalis broadly applicable in different chemical industries. Some other applications of zirconium alloys are used in everyday life as an opacifier, whitening agent, designs used on pottery and ceramics. The potential applications of Zirconium used in lamp filaments, jet engines, abrasives and in space shuttle parts. Zirconia is a biomaterial and has clinical applications.

Keywords

Zr-Sn-Fe-Cr alloy samples, 0.05M ammonium acetate + 0.05M citric acid by using galvanostatic anodic polarization, multidisiplinary applications.

INTRODUCTION

Zr-Sn-Fe-Cr alloy is a material science which involves to study the structure of material/sample which is relating them to their mechanical and electrical properties etc. Material properties are intensive properties i.e. they are independent of the amount of mass and varies from place to place within the system at any moment. Zr-Sn-Fe-Cr alloy in mechanical properties to apply for the structural applications, material properties are crucial and engineers can consider them.

When valve metals such as zirconium and its alloys like Zr – 2, Zr – 4, etc are anodically polarized, interference colored oxide films are formed. These smooth and mechanically perfect anodic films can act as dielectrics in capacitors. The phenomenon of anodic oxidation plays a basic role in micro-circuitry (1) and in thin film methods (2). Zirconia containing ceramics are materials of importing toughness (known as transformation toughening [3]. Zirconia has attracted considerable attention because of its diverse practical applications in fuel-cell technology[4]. As a novel nanomaterial ZrO₂ has made recent development in the field of biological applications in recent years[5,6,7]. Zirconium (Zr) alloys (e.g. Zircaloy-4) have many applications in light water reactors (LWRs)[8].

Molecular engineering or molecular nanotechnology or as it is more commonly known, nanotechnology, is the control of matter at the nanoscale with measurements between 1 and 100nm[9]. Anodic oxide films formed on valve metals are useful in the field of electrical and electronic components (such as capacitors, resistors, dioxides and photo electric devices), corrosion protection and for decorative purposes. Applications of anodic films have been reviewed [10]. Guntherschultze and Betz [11] were the first to investigate the kinetics and mechanism of the anodic oxidation of metals. Zirconia has great application prospect for its excellent properties in the industrial production [12]. The scientific research aim is to describe the oxide film growth kinetics by using faraday 1st law.

Material and Research Experimental Technique

Zircaloy-4 was of 98% nominal purity, supplied in the form of plate by **Nuclear Fuel Complex [NFC], Hyderabad** as a **gift sample**. **Thinning of Zircaloy-4 plate was done by Defence Metallurgical Research Lab [DMRL], Hyderabad**. Cutting of the thinned sheet was done at **tools and techniques, Balanagar, Hyderabad**.

The chemical composition of zircaloy-4:

0.07 wt. % **Cr**; 0.23 wt. % **Fe**; 1.44 wt. % **Sn** and balance is **Zr**.

In this scientific research work

The foil samples used were cut with the aid of a punch into flag-shaped specimens of 1 cm² working area on both side and 1½ cm long tag .

The chemical polish: HNO₃ : HF :H₂O = 3:3:1.

Galvanostatic Technique / Anodic Polarization of Zircaloy-4:

The galvanostatic anodic polarization of zircaloy-4 experiments were carried out in **electrochemistry laboratory** at university college of science, department of chemistry, **Osmania University**.

Zircaloy-4: Working Electrode.

A platinum sheet: The Counter Electrode (2x3 cm, weight 3.000 gm).

Anodic Polarization: A Double Walled Glass Cell [100mL capacity] was used.

The research experiments were carried out in an electrolyte, 0.05M ammonium acetate added in 0.05M citric acid.

Constant Current Density: $8\text{mA}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$ was used for experiments.

The experimental procedure for the anodic polarization by faraday 1st law is given elsewhere [13].

RESULTS

Anodic Polarization of zircaloy-4:

Kinetic measurements: Anodic films were formed on separate samples of zircaloy-4 in 0.05M ammonium acetate+ 0.05M citric acid at a constant current density of $8\text{mA}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$ and at room temperature. The conventional plots were drawn for all the experiments and given in **Fig-89, 90 and 91**.

Kinetic Parameters:

Zircaloy-4 material was Anodically polarized upto the electrical breakdown voltage in concentration of 0.05M ammonium acetate+ 0.05M citric acid at a constant current density of $8\text{mA}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$ at room temperature.

The anodization time and the capacitance of the anodized zirconia film formed were measured at an interval of 10V by interrupting the constant current circuit. Thickness of the oxide film were estimated by capacitance measurements.

The parameters of the zirconia oxide films surface studies:

Figure- 89 studied for anodization rate,

Figure-90 studied for capacitance to measure the thickness of oxide film and

Figure-91 studied for differential field.

The results have shown below through the conventional plots and **The conventional plots were drawn for all the experiments .**

1] The Anodization Voltage vs. AnodizationTime plot: double LINEAR.

2] The Reciprocal Capacitance vs. AnodizationTime plot: LINEAR.

3] The Reciprocal Capacitance vs. Anodization Voltage plot: LINEAR.

From these plots the Anodization Rate, Current Efficiency & Differential Field were estimated and are summarized in Table 1.

Figure 89: The plot of Anodization Voltage Vs. AnodizationTime.

Figure 90: The plot of Reciprocal Capacitance Vs. AnodizationTime.

Figure 91: The plot of Reciprocal Capacitance Vs. Anodization Voltage

Table 1: Anodic oxide films formed on zircaloy-4 in 0.05M AA+ 0.05M CA.

Electrolyte 0.05+0.05M	Anodization Rate $V.s^{-1}$	Current Efficiency η , (%)	Differential Field $F_D(MV.cm^{-1})$
AA + CA	0.92	70.73	4.615

DISCUSSIONS

Anodic polarization of zircaloy-4 by galvanostatic technique done in two different electrolytes added in same concentrations [0.05M ammonium acetate + 0.05M citric acid]. It was found that when voltage increased at constant current density which leads to maximum finely microstructure of the oxide films. The current distribution over the material surface were determined by current efficiency.

When reviewing the first-generation ceramic biomaterials the most commonly employed are alumina, zirconia and several porous ceramics. these non-metallic inorganic materials have a limited range of formulations. The microstructure is highly dependent on the applied manufacturing process (maximum temperature duration of the thermal steps purity of the powder, size and distribution of the grains and porosity) and it has a clear and direct effect on both the mechanical and biological properties[14].

It was investigated that the oxide film formed on the Zr-Sn-Fe-Cr alloy consisting of two discrete beautiful colour layers have observed upto 100V, later at the breakdown voltage appeared as a single coloured layer due to the incorporation of acetate and citrate anions. The added acetate and citrate anions get incorporated between the ionic vacancy sites of the metal oxide film and reduces the height of energy barrier of the movement of ions from one ionic site to another there by increasing the current. This incorporation of acetate and citrate anions increases the current efficiency with much ionic current gets utilization for film formation, which implies better kinetic results.

Zirconia ceramics have several advantages over other ceramic materials due to the transformation toughening mechanisms operating in their microstructure that can give to components made out of them, very interesting mechanical properties [15].

The anodization voltage vs. anodization time plot of **Figure.1** was found to be double linear up to the breakdown voltage. The breakdown voltage was observed to be for zirconia (ZrO_2) at constant current density **8 mA.cm⁻²**. The change in anodizing voltage over the course of the **Zr-Sn-Fe-Cr alloy** oxidation at the maximum breakdown voltage is below 200V shown in **Figure.1**. we have been observed a fast and double linear increase in the voltage from **[0 to <200V]**. We were observed a decrease in the anodization rate **[0.92 oV.s⁻¹] of voltage increase upto the breakdown voltage.**

The effect at constant current density, the composition and concentration of electrolyte and the nature to the metal on the features of electrical breakdown and the value of breakdown voltage were studied. **We detected the breakdown voltage as a visible spark.** The anodic coating was formed below the potential when the oxide layer breakdown occurs as a **visible spark**.

In Figure-2, The film growth process involves the movement of oxygen ions from the acetate and citrate anions of the electrolyte into the zircaloy-4. The capacitance increased in microfarads and the current efficiency increased in better yield. The platinum electrode is the cathode where reduction occurs. in an aqueous solution of $2H^+$ ions from the electrolyte, the reaction is the reduction of water to form hydrogen gas. Here platinum is an inert electrode that means does not participate in the reaction itself but it facilitates the electron transfer.

We were found that during anodic polarziation the surface oxide grown with an in homogenous coverage on zircaloy-4 surface. Due to the incorporation of anions from the electrolyte to the surface oxide changed the surface chemistry. The research material we used is also applicable for therapeutic modifications of zirconia which acts as bioactive material for advancing dental implants. The surface modifications are enhanced to improve zirconia properties. These surface coatings on Zr-4 sample/material were introduced as surface treatments would enhance bioactivity biocompatibility or potential, antibacterial properties of zirconia.

As a result the surface modification of **Zr-Sn-Fe-Cr alloy** based implants have been performed by using **galvanostatic anodic polarization** at the macro-micro and nanoscales.

CONCLUSION

The anodic polarization technique facilitates the fabrication of a colour coated zirconia oxide layer with a microstructure on the cladding surface. Among the kinetic parameters, the Capacitance measurements determines the zirconia store electrical energy, effectively it conduct charge. Anodization rate decreased estimates the thickness of zirconia oxide films, current efficiency yield evaluates the electrical charge transfer estimated good yield. **Acetate anions and citrate anions incorporation zirconia exhibits much higher capacitance. Faraday 1st law governs the anodization of zirconia oxide films with the current yield percentage indicates the percentage of current used for film growth kinetically improved due to the constant current density .** zirconia oxide films are using in nuclear industry and in natural science [physics, chemistry, geology and biology]. Some other applications of zirconium alloys are used in everyday life as an opacifier, whitening agent, designs used on pottery and ceramics. The potential applications of Zirconium used in lamp filaments, jet engines, abrasives and in space shuttle parts. Zirconia is a biomaterial, biomedical applications and has clinical applications also. The surface modifications are the route to enhance biocompatibility of permanent implants.

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